

Institutional framework of Waste management in the EU and its implementation in Greece, environmental impact & health

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This research aimed to determine the application level of European Union legislations of waste management, due to their effects on the environment & health, in Greece. An in-depth investigation was carried out at European, national and local level, both legislative, judicial, executive and applicative level, regarding the effects on public health and the environment of waste management. It analyses European and Greek legislations, combined with judicial decisions and compares the adoption of those strategies aimed at conserving natural resources, ensuring the health and promoting the well-being of citizens and environmental protection. A mixed method approach was used, the research combines qualitative analysis with European and Greek courts and parliaments and quantitative analysis with questionnaires to technical and structural services directors in Greece. It examines cases of adequacy and applicability of the current European legislations in Greece.

Index Terms: Waste Management; Natural resources; Public Health; Environmental impact; legislation; sustainable implementation; European Union; Greece.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the many definitions of waste, is substances or objects that no longer serve the purpose for which they were made for and that their possessor wants or is obliged to discard. What waste is, is based on how it is disposed of. However, the main issue is minimizing them.[1][2][3]

Pollution is inversely proportional to per capita income, without implying that rising per capita income is the only cause of environmental degradation. The definition of waste and the analysis of its meaning are based on how it is disposed of.[1][2] However, the key step in waste management is to minimize its production.[3]

Other factors are the increase in trade, the growth of the financial sector and public spending as well as the institutional factors set by governments.[4] There are many different interpretations regarding the definition and management of waste. These differences lie in the different interpretations given by the governments of different states, depending on the environmental policy they follow.

Waste management is crucial to building a sustainable agenda. To a large extent, the current legislation around the world ignores, in a way, the already existing waste, as some countries focus mainly on the prevention of waste generation rather than managing what already exists.

Consequently, despite the express will to prevent the creation of waste, implicitly, the legislation effectively simply "tolerates" the accumulation of waste. [5]

The reuse of waste is considered more as a potential pollutant than a raw material.⁶ This results in useful materials being considered wastes.[1]

According to the European Union (EU), "waste" means any substance or object of defined categories, which the owner discards or is obliged to discard.[7]

For the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), waste is items of radioactive material intended for disposal.[8]

For the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) waste is substances or objects that are discarded or intended to be disposed of or required to be disposed of by national law.[9]

According to LOX waste is either products of "non-economic value" from an industrial system ("negative market") or any substance or object that has been "used" for its intended purpose by the consumer or "served its intended purpose" and will not be reused.[10]

McKinney [11] and Baran [12] refer to waste as the result of a system's inadequacy, while Hollander¹³ sees waste as something that must be extracted to achieve some result. Elwood and Patashik¹⁴ refer to waste by giving it a human-related meaning, considering that instead of trying to identify the material referred to as waste, we should analyze the activity that resulted in the creation of waste.

Waste management seems to be merely a reaction to its existence. We can say that there is a conflict of the duality of waste politics: if we define waste at the point of its creation, how can we avoid its creation?

II. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT & HEALTH

The toxicity of various substances in the waste categories is considered a cause of carcinogenesis in those exposed to high levels of these, according to animal and human health studies. [1] [15-19]

In addition to carcinogenesis, many of these toxic substances can cause damage to the central nervous system, liver, kidneys, heart, lungs, skin, reproductive system, etc. Studies of air pollution have shown that there may be effects on morbidity and mortality, particularly in vulnerable groups such as the elderly. There have been many extensive studies and detailed epidemiology reviews, in hundreds of regions, investigating the effects of waste toxicity on human and animal health. [16-19]

Also, studies have shown that the existence of genetic abnormalities and reproductive disorders is associated with high concentrations of pollutant-waste. In particular, Vianna and Polan 1984 [20] and Goldman et al 1985 [21] documented a significant decline in births in populations around the Love Canal site during the period it was used as a landfill (1940–1953). Accordingly, low birth rates as well as a large increase in infant mortality and an increase in cancers were observed in many parts of the USA [22-27] and Great Britain [28-31].

Epidemiological studies show the negative health effects of waste exposure [32][33] with the effects being more severe in children, the elderly, and vulnerable groups.[34]

A correlation between exposure to particulates present in waste and their negative health effects, have shown, such as increased mortality or emergency admission to hospitals, particularly of patients with cardiovascular and respiratory problems [32][33] while the effects appear to be more severe in vulnerable groups such as children, the elderly or people with chronic conditions such as asthma or pre-existing cardiovascular disease [34].

The variety of substances present in the waste leaves no doubt about the existence of a risk of contamination of the air, the soil and of course the waters with a direct risk to animals and humans health.[35]

Proper waste management is a priority in the context of the European Union's environmental policy.[1]

III. INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK OF WASTE MANAGEMENT IN THE EU AND GREECE

In developing countries, waste rate generation is increasing in line with population, economic development and urbanization of society. [36] Local government, as the main person responsible for waste management, faces several problems such as lack of organization, financial resources and complexity of legislation.[1][37]

The legislation of the European Union member states influenced by EU regulations, which derive from its primary objective that all of its member states must, by harmonizing their legislation in a single Community action. Thus, for Waste management, member states have to achieve the same standards but are subjected to the legislative competence of national parliaments.

The E.U. policy for environmental protection, is based on preventive actions, remediation of environmental disasters and in a principle that "polluter pays". [38][39]

Waste management in Europe shows a complexity of proposals that lead to environmental, economic, social and regulatory impact practices which complicate the analysis of a regional policy. [40]

In addition to strict legal commitments, political decisions and resolutions of international organizations have a significant influence on Environmental Policy, as they set rules that cultivate a sense of responsibility and obligation to change the behaviour of the states themselves.

This is in contrast to the low priority given by politicians to the issue of waste compared to other local self-government activities⁴¹ with the end result of having untrained and specialized staff in local administration [42]. When referring to environmental law and the obligations arising from it, the political dimension of the issues must also be recognized, as this area is by no means an isolated area of law. [43]

Many countries use the "pay as you throw" system. The level of its implementation varies greatly by country and also within countries such as in Belgium. However, all countries with recycling rates above 45% use a similar system, while most countries with recycling rates below 20% do not, indicating that the system "pay as you throw" is an effective means of recycling. [43]

When it comes to waste, and especially on the subject of landfills, Denmark, the Netherlands and Belgium have the highest percentages of achieving the objectives of the E.U. On the contrary, Greece has the lowest percentages of achieving the objectives according to the E.U. (N.A. Doukas, 2024. fig. 1) [1]

All countries giving landfill rates well below the EU average of 28% have either banned landfilling of biodegradable or mixed municipal waste or combined the ban with a landfill tax of at least €30/tonne. The countries with recycling rates below 30%, with the exception of Greece, entered the EU in 2004 or later, and therefore started implementing recycling policies later than the rest of the member states. [44] For example, only the recent condemnation of Greece for a single

illegal dump in the area of Kourouptios in Crete cost the country 4.7 million euros, while a fine of 10 million euros was upheld by the EU Court of Justice. Because Greece had not yet adopted a special plan for the management of hazardous waste, but neither had it created an integrated and appropriate network of facilities for the disposal of hazardous waste or implemented "historical waste" management by the deadline of March 25, 2013 [45].

Greece since 1986 to 2018 has legislated more than 12 laws on waste and environmental protection. If one includes in these laws the Presidential Decrees, along with the Ministerial decisions, will notice that the number of legislations are more than doubled. [46]

The National Waste Management Plan (NWMP) of Greece in accordance with articles 22 and 35 of Law 4042/2012 [47], which incorporated article 28 of Directive 2008/98/EC, aimed to provide the appropriate strategic directions, so that through a set of plans, programs, actions and projects institutionalize the goals and limitations of the negative effects of waste at the national level. [48]

According to article 31 § 1 of Law 4342/2015, the National Waste Prevention Program is sanctioned by Decision of the Ministers of Interior, Administrative Reconstruction and Environment - Energy.

The Council of Ministers can modify them, if it deems it necessary. By joint decision of the Minister of Environment and Energy and the Ministers of the other co-competent agencies, the Special National Plans for the Management of Waste Streams are approved, which require a more specific overall treatment at country level.

In article 13 of Law 4071/2012, in essence, the responsibilities for solid waste management are separated after the SWMA and the Municipalities.

As exclusively responsible for the drafting - preparation or amendment of the regional waste management plans (RWMP) of § 2 of article 35 of Law 4042/2012, in accordance with Law 4555/2018 the "Regional Waste Management Plan Planning agency" (APRWMP) are defined. In particular, in accordance with article 22 of Law 4042/2012, which has already been repealed by virtue of article 74 of Law 4819/2021, the minimum data - elements that should be included in a waste management plan were established and provided for, but also some additional elements, which at the discretion of the competent Ministry, could be included - added. Finally, in par. 4 of article 22 of the same Law, explicit mention is made of the obligation of compliance of each project with Directives 94/62/EC and 1991/31/EC.

Local Waste Management Plans (LWMP) are defined as the operational plans drawn up by Municipalities for the management of their waste to meet the objectives of the NWMP, in order to be evaluated and integrated by the competent body during the preparation process and approval of the relevant Regional Waste Management Plans (RWMP). [49]

It thus becomes clear that member states of the EU, despite the fact that following the same legislative framework, there is poor compliance with what is defined in the European policy and the national framework for waste management. Social influences, altruists and regulatory factors are reasons why some communities have developed strong recycling habits. [50][51]

Therefore, in order to establish whether the Greek legislation is sufficient or not, an examination of various cases of EU countries will follow, with which Greece shares and applies the same Community framework and has incorporated the same European Directives.

IV. METHOD ANALYSIS

A mixed method approach was used, the research combines qualitative analysis (A) with European and Greek legislations, courts and parliaments and quantitative analysis (B) with questionnaires.

A. qualitative analysis:

Significant differences observed among the EU Member States regarding the use they made of these various treatment methods. For instance, some Member States had very high recycling rates (Italy, Belgium, Slovakia and Latvia), in others, landfill is the prevailing treatment category (Romania, Bulgaria, Finland, Sweden and Greece). (N.A. Doukas, 2024. fig. 1) [1]

In particular, waste management in Denmark is characterized by a high degree of incineration, which reached 54% in 2010. It is the highest percentage and the highest amount per capita in the EU of 27 (Eurostat, 2012). [52]

In order to assess Denmark's prospects for the 50% recycling target as defined in the framework directive 2008/98/EC, three scenarios were calculated (figure 1). [52]

Besides Denmark, the Netherlands is also among the first countries with the highest rates of waste incineration. More than 64% of their waste is recycled - and most of the rest is incinerated to generate electricity. Therefore, only a small percentage ends up in a landfill. [52]

In this case, in order to assess the Netherlands' prospects for meeting the 50% waste recycling target, within the framework of compliance with Directive 2008/98/EC, three scenarios were calculated (Figure 2). [53]

In Figure 2 can be seen that the Netherlands has already achieved the 50% target for 2020 since 2007. The Netherlands has had consistently high rates in recent years estimated to reach 55% to 60% by 2020. [53]

As early as 1995, the Dutch government issued a waste ordinance that introduced a ban on 35 categories of waste, including all fuels and biodegradable waste. Exceptionally, the decree allows local authorities to grant exemption from this ban to landfill operators, provided that there is prior assurance from the national environmental authorities, that there is no alternative treatment solution other than the landfill for the specific waste [54].[53]

The Dutch approach, however, is quite different from that of Denmark. The Dutch approach promotes avoiding the creation of as much waste as possible, recovering valuable raw materials from it, producing energy by incinerating residual waste and only then disposing of what is left - but in an environmentally friendly way.

Belgium as a country has already achieved the 50% recycling target as defined for waste in the framework Directive 2008/98/EC, of GDP for 2020. Flanders had already achieved its target before 2001. [53]

From the diagram in Figure 3, it appears that Italy was able to achieve the 50% recycling target by 2020, set by Directive 2008/98/EC, even if the increase in recycling followed the period 2001-2005 which was the worst-case scenario.

The institutional regulation of the waste industry is facing a deep reform process in Italy. It mainly focuses on the creation of new administrative units, the so-called *Ambiti Territoriali Ottimali* (ATO) (Optimal Territorial Sector).

Italy strives and emphasizes the field of composting through the intensive separation of organic matter. Intensive separation of organics (ISSO) represents a strategic decision of Italy to achieve an overall high efficiency of domestic source separation systems. It has a dual purpose, to maximize the diversion of organic materials from landfills and to reduce the amount of hazardous materials in residual waste to less than 10%.

Finally, as far as Greece is concerned, the recycling of waste and especially MSW has increased by more than 10% in recent years. This increase is mainly due to the coordinated efforts to recycle materials, with organic recycling still being very low and hovering around 1%. In addition, in Greece, over 80% of municipal solid waste was disposed of in landfills in 2010 and therefore the EU's 75% reduction target was not possible to fulfill, until 2010, for landfills, despite the 4-year grace period granted to Greece. [55]

Figure 4 and Figure 5, captures the evolution of MSW production per capita and in percentages, respectively, to total recycling material and organic recycling (fertilizer and other biological treatment) in Greece from 2001 to 2010, where there has been a slow but gradual increase throughout these years.

Figure 6 shows the recycling percentage of the produced MSW for the years 2001-2010 in Greece. In order to achieve the goal, set by the E.U. for recycling levels in the country, a linear regression was applied to three scenarios. This linear regression was calculated for each of these scenarios and extended to 2020, the EU target year. All scenarios led to a recycling level between 25% and 33% of the MSW produced, as Figure 6 shows. [55]

Under the EU Landfill Directive, member states had to reduce the percentage of biodegradable municipal waste they sent to landfill by a certain percentage. However, Greece is among the EU countries that still maintain high landfill rates. In fact, the amount of MSW in Greece in 2010 was equivalent to 81% of all municipal waste (figure 7).

B. quantitative analysis:

Questionnaire is a scientific quantitative research method, on the basis of which the researcher can collect data and information in order to investigate the subject matter of his research [56].

For the needs of the research and given the effort to investigate the compliance and effectiveness of the measures taken by the Local Government Organizations (Municipalities and Regions), it is important to examine various variables with the questionnaire method, which was chosen as the most suitable for gathering measurable results and drawing safe conclusions.

Questionnaire was drawn up, addressed to Service Managers whose object is the waste management of Municipalities and Regions, consisting of twenty-four (24) questions and one hundred and fifty-four (154) questionnaires were collected from the three hundred and forty-five (345) Municipalities and Regions of the country, while their anonymity and non-identification was fully ensured. After collecting the data, the data from the questionnaires were processed with the program "Qualtrics XM". [1]

Regarding the period of time for the start of planning and implementation of Decentralized Waste Management Plans in the context of national and regional planning, 65.2% of respondents answered the period 2015-2017 and 68.8% answered that these Plans satisfy the objectives of the National Waste Management Plan in moderate grade.

59.4% of the respondents considered the existing legislation satisfactory while 69% of respondents answered that the legislation is applicable to moderate grade with what this may entail for drawing conclusions as to the means available to those who are called to finally implement it at the level of Local Government.

More specifically and illustratively, in figure 8, we can see a correlation of the measures for the prevention of pollution and the general degradation of the environment taken by the Local Government Organizations with the degree of solid waste management, so that raw materials are saved and reused (P-Value= 0.00001). The main part of figure 8 moves to grade 3=moderate grade with 4=satisfactory, with waste management moving close to grade 3 and prevention measures close to 4. This can also be understood from figure 12, where we see the main percentage of the measures to be in the moderate rating. We observe that the local authorities take measures at satisfactory levels, but they deliver on moderate

ratings. In other words, we notice that some efforts are being made to save raw materials and to reuse them, but more attention and development is needed in this area.

As shown in Figure 9, in average values, the average of the measures taken is 55.4% in contrast to the extent to which solid waste is managed to save raw materials and reuse them as much as possible, which is 44.6%. In other words, we observe that the Local Government Organizations take measures at satisfactory levels, but they yield to a moderate degree. This means that although some efforts are being made to save raw materials and reuse them, more attention and development is needed in this area.

Figure 10 shows the correlation of the average waste production per inhabitant with the measures taken to prevent pollution and the general degradation of the environment by the Local Government Organizations (P-Value= 0.0009) where here again we see that the main volume of measurements for waste produced (kgr)/inhabitant is 300kgr/inhabitant and above.

It becomes clear that the vast majority of Local Government Organizations, i.e. 96.8% of them, have made efforts to raise awareness among their citizens with the lion's share of the use of information brochures/announcements (at a rate of 69%) (N.A. Doukas, 2024. fig. 2) [1] and with days/conferences/events (at a rate of 25%) (figure 11).

The greatest effort to take measures to prevent pollution and the general degradation of the environment is paid by the Local Government Organizations of the first and second degree in which more than 300 kgr of waste/inhabitant are produced, a fact that could be characterized as expected since the said Municipalities have a greater burden of managing their waste (fig. 12).

Although the majority of local authorities stated that they took measures to prevent pollution and general environmental degradation to a moderate or satisfactory grade (Figure 13), managed to implement the preparation for reuse and recycling on the total of Municipal Solid Waste only at a rate of 1%-25%, to reduce the waste disposed of in Sanitary Landfills to a small and moderate grade and increase the amount of collection of recyclable materials with an emphasis on packaging materials and Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment in moderate grade (N.A. Doukas, 2024. fig. 3-4) [1].

The paradox is that the majority of local governments that took moderate, satisfactory or excellent measures to prevent pollution and environmental degradation, started to design and implement Waste Management Plans in the years 2015-2017 (N.A. Doukas, 2024. fig. 4) [1], with these being applied by 68.8% to moderate grade (Figure 14).

Figure 15, highlights the relationship between the adequacy of waste laws and their enforceability (P-Value= 0.00001), that 59.4% of the interviewed heads of local governments considered the existing legislation sufficiently satisfactory while 69% of respondents answered that the legislation is applicable to moderate grade. (N.A. Doukas, 2024. fig. 4) [1].

V. CONCLUSION-DISCUSSION

From the above, it can be concluded that the waste management system implemented by the Local Government Organizations has neither the desired nor the expected results. The local governments must put more effort into the efficient implementation and further improvement of the Decentralized Waste Management Plans that they have drawn up. It is considered appropriate for the Local Government Organizations to intervene by submitting proposals so that the provisions that run through the national waste management legislation become more complete and more applicable.

As already underlined, environmental legislation is not an isolated area. It is completely connected to the political priorities as well as the administrative capacity of each state to adapt to modern and pressing challenges. Precisely for this reason, its effective application requires some basic conditions. It requires structures, infrastructure, qualified and sufficient staff, political will, monitoring, controls, etc. [43]

According to Feller G.:

"We cannot simply go from landfill to recycling. It's not something that can be done overnight by buying a few new collector vehicles. By taking measures to increase segregation at source, we can ensure that less and less waste is sent to landfill. But then we'll have to know what we're going to do with that material." (Feller, G. 2010). [57]

Based on the literature and according to this research, the lack of technical skills among local and state authorities [58], inadequate infrastructure [41], poor roads and vehicles [59], and inadequate technologies [60] emerge as factors that negatively affect the waste management system. Also, factors affecting the environmental aspect of waste management in developing countries are the lack of environmental control systems and the assessment of real impacts. [61][62] Finally, the very high costs required for these services [63], the lack of financial support⁶⁴, the limited resources and the lack of proper use of finances create obstacles to proper waste management. As mentioned by Sharholy (2008) [65], the participation of the private sector is a factor that could improve the efficiency of the system. [66]

In summary, the decision on how to manage waste depends mainly on two factors, environmental and economic, and usually depends on political decisions and the strength of local, national and global markets.

Figure 1. MSW recycling in Denmark. Source: European Environment Agency, 2013.

Figure 2. MSW recycling in the Netherlands. Source: European Environment Agency, 2013.

Figure 3. MSW Recycling in Italy. Source: European Environment Agency, 2013.

Figure 4. MSW production per capita in Greece. Source: European Environment Agency, 2013.

Figure 5. MSW Recycling in Greece. Percentages are calculated as % of MSW produced. Source: European Environment Agency, 2013.

Figure 6. MSW Recycling in Greece. Source: European Environment Agency, 2013.

Figure 7. Sanitary landfill of biodegradable MSW in Greece. Source: European Environment Agency, 2013. Data for 2010 are CRI estimates. Note: The target dates take into account Greece's 4-year derogation period.

Figure 8. Correlation of measures taken by Local Authorities to prevent pollution and general environmental degradation and how they serve it. (Questionnaire survey by the author, 2023)

Figure 9. (Questionnaire survey by the author, 2023)

Figure 10. Correlation of the average waste production per inhabitant (kgr) and the measures taken by Local Authorities to prevent pollution and general environmental degradation. (Questionnaire survey by the author, 2023)

Figure 11. (Questionnaire survey by the author, 2023)

Means of raising awareness and encouraging the active participation of citizens.

- Leaflets/Announcements
- Seminars/Conferences/Events
- Social media
- Other

Figure 12. Correlation of pollution prevention and general environmental degradation with the average waste production per inhabitant (kgr) and the degree of solid waste management (Questionnaire survey by the author, 2023)

Figure 13. (Questionnaire survey by the author, 2023)
Average degree that the Local Government Organizations have taken measures to prevent pollution and general degradation of the environment.

Figure 14. (Questionnaire survey by the author, 2023)

To what extent do the "Waste Management Plans" drawn up by the Local Government Organizations you serve satisfy the objectives of the National Waste Management Plan?

Figure15. Correlation of effectiveness and applicability of legislation (Questionnaire survey by the author, 2023)

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